

Site Suitability Analysis for Small Dams for Irrigation and Flood Control in Anaku, Ayamelum Local Government Area, Anambra State

Nnalue, P.A¹, Emengini, E.J.¹

¹Department of Surveying and Geoinformatics, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka Nigeria.

Abstract: *Water is an undervalued resource, and dams can mitigate irrigation water scarcity and flood effects. Therefore, this research aims to conduct a site suitability analysis for small dams to tackle the challenges of irrigation and flood control in Anaku, Ayamelum local government area of Anambra State, Nigeria. The objective is to identify suitable sites for constructing small dams using a Geographic Information System (GIS) approach. To achieve this objective, several steps were undertaken. Firstly, a comprehensive land cover/land use feature map was created to understand the existing characteristics of the study area. Criteria for modeling site suitability were then established, including topographic factors (such as slope), geological factors, soil type, land cover/use, precipitation, flow accumulation, and proximity to rivers. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was utilized for pair-wise comparisons to assign weights to each criterion. Through ArcGIS, weighted overlay analysis was conducted to combine and assess the various criteria, resulting in a site suitability map that identifies potential locations for small dams based on the summation of weights assigned to each contributing factor. The results indicated that 70% of Anaku was suitable for dam siting, with Umuria identified as the most suitable village in Anaku. This mapping method provides crucial data for decision-makers involved in regional water resources management and sustainable development. It facilitates the determination of optimal sites for constructing new dams, serving purposes such as irrigation and flood control.*

Keywords: *Anaku, Irrigation, Flood, Suitability, Anambra State*

1. Introduction

Water is of great importance to the world economy. It plays a part in numerous human activities such as the production, sourcing and sustenance of agricultural products, long-distance trade of commodities, energy generation, domestic and industrial processes and sports and entertainment. As stated in Baroni *et al* (2007), approximately 70% of the freshwater used by humans goes to agriculture. However, freshwater availability is likely to be one of the major societal challenges of the twenty-first century.

Due to unplanned urbanization, limited water resources, and ineffective regulations for managing water supply and distribution, developing countries are more vulnerable to water scarcity than developed countries (Hagos *et al.*, 2022). This scarcity is one of the biggest human problems in developing countries, especially in semi-arid regions where it can form an obstacle to irrigation and cultivation, cattle raising and human survival. Therefore, preservation of agricultural production capacity and quality of human health in developing countries requires a solution focused on water conservation sanitation.

Nigeria is one of the developing countries facing this major water crisis. Its economy is agricultural-based, hence agriculture and rural development are vital. Agriculture accounts on average about 30 to 40 percent of the nominal Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employs about 65 to 75 percent of the labor force, while providing various ecosystem services (NBS, 2017). The farming system is dominated by smallholder rural farmers who account for about 80 to 90 percent of producers. In the rural areas of Southeast Nigeria, farming is the predominant livelihood activity. Anambra State is important in this region because of their large-scale involvement in agricultural activities and high dependence of other Southeastern states on them for food and goods which takes care of their feeding and trading respectively (Nnadi *et al.*, 2019). Anambra state is also the major grower and supplier of rice in Southeast Nigeria (Nnadi *et al.*, 2019).

The need to have a continuous and stable water supply for human activities implies building dams and/or reservoirs to store water during the rainy season and use it in the drought season (Sayl *et al.*, 2016). Dams are structural barriers built across streams, rivers or waterways to store and safely retain large amounts of water, which is then released for a variety of purposes including irrigation, hydropower, recreation, water supply and flood protection.

Global water use is growing rapidly, surpassing population growth due to factors like increased population and agricultural demands (Moe and Rheingans, 2006). This has led to chronic water shortages in many regions, including Anaku in Ayamelum Local Government Area of Anambra State (Onugba and Yaya, 2010). These shortages result in communicable diseases, reduced vitality, and hindered productivity. Anaku's heavy reliance on rain-fed agriculture also makes it vulnerable to climate change impacts (Madu *et al.*, 2010). Constructing dams and reservoirs can help provide water supplies and support irrigation, improving rural livelihoods (Senzanjeet *et al.*, 2008). However, dam siting in Anaku poses challenges, such as identifying suitable locations, considering ecological and environmental impacts, and assessing social and economic factors (Shah *et al.*, 2012). Geological stability and engineering feasibility must also be assessed for long-term safety (IRBM, 2010). Additionally, flood control measures need to be incorporated into dam design to mitigate potential adverse effects downstream (IRBM, 2010). Resolving these challenges is crucial for establishing sustainable water supply infrastructure and enhancing community resilience.

2. Materials and Method

2.1. Study Area

Anaku is one of the 8 communities in the Ayamelum Local Government Area (LGA) of Anambra State. It lies at Longitude 6° 55' 44" E and Latitude 6° 28' 7" N and covers an estimated surface area of 7200 km². It is bordered by "Omambala," the native name of the Anambra River, which is a tributary of the famous River Niger (North), Ezu River (South), Omor and Umuerum communities (East). The area is underlain by Cretaceous to recent sedimentary formations of the Anambra Basin. The Basin is dominantly filled with clastic sediments constituting several distinct lithostratigraphic units ranging from Upper Campanian to Recent in age (Nfor *et al.*, 2007). Most of the dwellers in Anaku are crop farmers and fisher folks who cultivate mainly rice, as well as other crops (yam, cassava, vegetables, and cocoyam) and also engage actively in daily fishing activities from the Omambala river.

2.2. Methodology

The hydrological analysis like the flow direction, flow accumulation and stream networks were used to determine areas with high or low water accumulation rate and its tributaries. The analysis of the inundated areas was conducted by generating watershed map of the study area. The watershed map determines the spatial coverage or extent of areas liable for flooding in the event of overflow especially at the confluence. Surface Analysis was carried out to determine the slope, contour and TIN (Triangulated Irregular Network) of the study area.

3. Results

3.1 Identification and Selection of Criteria

The most suitable site for a dam was determined using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). The selection criteria and requirements, as detailed in Table 1, were crucial components in guiding the research process.

Table 1: Criteria

S/N	Criterion	Requirement
1	Elevation	Elevation between 35m to 44m
2	Land Cover/ Land Use	Paved Surfaces, proximity to floodplains
3	Rainfall	>2650mm annual rainfall
4	Geology	Non-Carbonate Sedimentary Rock
5	Slope	Between 1 and 5 degrees
6	Drainage Network	<500m drainage networks
7	Flow Accumulation	< 500m from high-flow accumulation pixels
8	Drainage Basin	Largest watershed in the area
9	Soil	Red soil, clay, Brown soil

The necessary data to achieve the research goal based on the chosen criteria outlined in Table 1 were gathered. These data are shown below.

3.2 Reclassification and Standardization of Criteria

To start using the AHP and weighted linear combination model, the first step is reclassifying and standardizing the criteria. Each cell has a value for every input. Hence, the datasets are reclassified to a common measurement system, making it easier to compare them. In this research, all datasets were divided into two classes: most suitable areas and not suitable areas. This allows assigning values like 1 and 2 for each range of values. The reclassified and standardized criteria can be seen below.

3.3 Analytical Hierarchy Process and Determination of Criteria Weight

AHP facilitates the evaluation of benefits and risks by assigning numerical values to each criterion, reflecting their importance. This numeric scale ranges from 1 to 9, with 1 signifying equal importance and 9 indicating a clear superiority of one factor over another (see Table 4.1). Importantly, if a factor is deemed less important than another, this is conveyed through the reciprocal values (1/1 to 1/9).

The methodology relies on a ratio matrix, specifically the Eigenvector method, to gauge the comparative significance of one criterion against another. This structured approach ensures a comprehensive assessment, guiding decision-makers towards projects with the highest overall value or the most desirable benefits while minimizing associated risks.

Table 2: Relative Importance in Pairwise Comparison Source: (Saaty, 1980)

Judgment value	Description
1	Equal importance
3	Moderately importance
5	Strongly Importance
7	Very strongly important
9	Extremely important

3.3.1 Pairwise Comparison Matrix Formation

The formation of the pairwise comparison matrix involved inputting judgment values between factors as matrix elements, adhering to the foundational rules set by Saaty. This process, as illustrated in Table 2, facilitated the creation of Table 3, which is a result of the pairwise comparison matrix.

Table 3: Pair-wise comparison matrix of the study

Factor	Flow Acc	Basin	Drainage	Precipitation	LCLU	Geology	Elevation	Slope	Soil
Flow Acc	1.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	7.00
Basin	0.50	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00
Drainage	0.50	0.50	1.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	6.00
Precipitation	0.33	0.33	0.50	1.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00
LCLU	0.25	0.25	0.33	0.33	1.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	4.00
Geology	0.25	0.25	0.33	0.33	0.50	1.00	2.00	2.00	3.00
Elevation	0.20	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.33	0.50	1.00	2.00	2.00
Slope	0.20	0.20	0.25	0.25	0.33	0.50	0.50	1.00	2.00
Soil	0.14	0.17	0.17	0.20	0.25	0.33	0.50	0.50	1.00
TOTAL	3.38	4.95	6.83	10.37	16.42	18.33	24.00	26.50	36.00

3.3.2 Computation of the Criterion Weights

After creating the pairwise comparison matrix, the computation of criteria weights involved several key operations:

- i. Finding the sum of values in each column of the pairwise comparison matrix.
- ii. Dividing each element in the matrix by its respective column total, resulting in a normalized pairwise comparison matrix.
- iii. Computing the average of elements in each row of the normalized matrix, achieved by dividing the sum of normalized scores for each row by the number of criteria. These averages serve as estimates of the relative weights of the compared criteria.

4.3.3 Normalized Pairwise Comparison Matrix

Table 3 illustrates the normalized pairwise comparison matrix that was generated. To elaborate on this with an example: consider the element in the normalized matrix corresponding to Flow Accumulation (row) against Flow Accumulation (column), denoted as the matrix element in the 1st row and 1st column. The

value 3.38 in the pairwise comparison matrix represents the sum of elements in the second column, while 1 is the judgment value for Flow Accumulation (row) against Flow Accumulation (column). Therefore, the normalized value for F1, F1, is computed as $(1/3.38) = 0.30$, as presented in the table. This calculation follows the process of normalizing the pairwise comparison matrix, providing a clear representation of the relative weights and relationships between the criteria

Table 4.4: Normalized Pairwise Comparison Matrix

Factor	Flow Acc	Basin	Drainage	Precipitation	LCLU	Geology	Elevation	Slope	Soil	Mean
Flow Acc	0.30	0.40	0.29	0.29	0.24	0.22	0.21	0.19	0.19	0.26
Basin	0.15	0.20	0.29	0.29	0.24	0.22	0.17	0.19	0.17	0.21
Drainage	0.15	0.10	0.15	0.19	0.18	0.16	0.17	0.15	0.17	0.16
Precipitation	0.10	0.07	0.07	0.10	0.18	0.16	0.17	0.15	0.14	0.13
LCLU	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.06	0.11	0.13	0.11	0.11	0.08
Geology	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06
Elevation	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.08	0.06	0.04
Slope	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04
Soil	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02
TOTAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

3.3.4 Prioritization weight matrix

Table 3.4 presents the prioritized weight matrix, where each element is computed by dividing the normalized sum of each row by the total number of criteria. The resulting averages provide an estimate of the relative weights of the compared criteria. To illustrate, let's consider the criteria weight of Flow Accumulation as an example:

Flow Accumulation = $0.30 + 0.40 + 0.29 + 0.29 + 0.24 + 0.22 + 0.21 + 0.19 + 0.19$ (sum of the elements in row 1)

Total number of criteria in row 1 = 9

Therefore, $A \{ \text{weight of factor 1 (F1)} \} = 2.33/9 = 0.2588 = 0.26$

$A\%$ (criteria in percentage) = $A \times 100 = 0.26 * 100 = 26\%$, see table 4.5 for more details.

Table 3.5: Prioritization weight matrix

Factor	Flow Acc	Basin	Drainage	Precipitation	LCLU	Geology	Elevation	Slope	Soil	Mean	Weight (%)
Flow Acc	0.30	0.40	0.29	0.29	0.24	0.22	0.21	0.19	0.1	0.26	26
Basin	0.15	0.20	0.29	0.29	0.24	0.22	0.17	0.19	0.17	0.21	21
Drainage	0.15	0.10	0.15	0.19	0.18	0.16	0.17	0.15	0.17	0.16	16
Precipitation	0.10	0.07	0.07	0.10	0.18	0.16	0.17	0.15	0.14	0.13	13
LCLU	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.06	0.11	0.13	0.11	0.11	0.08	8
Geology	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	6
Elevation	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.08	0.06	0.04	4
Slope	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	4
Soil	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	2
TOTAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	100

3.3.5 Estimation of the Consistency Ratio

In this phase, the calculation of a Consistency Ratio (CR) was carried out to assess the reliability of the judgment values, especially concerning large samples of purely random judgments. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) explicitly addresses consistency because, in the process of making paired comparisons, individuals may not consistently apply logical reasoning. To determine the Consistency Ratio (CR), the AHP compares it against the Random Index (RI). Mathematically, the Consistency Ratio is defined as:

$$CR = RI / CI$$

In the calculation of the Consistency Ratio, the mathematical formula $CR = RI / CI$ was utilized. The Random Index (RI) represents the consistency index of a randomly generated pairwise comparison matrix of order 1 to 10, approximated through random indices. This ratio serves as a crucial metric to gauge the reliability and coherence of the decision-making process, accounting for the inherent challenge of maintaining consistency in human judgments.

Table 3.6: Random Index by Saaty

Size of matrix (n)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Random index (RI)	0	0	0.58	0.9	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.46	1.49

Source: (Saaty, 2001).

Note: If the value of the obtained Consistency Ratio is less than 0.1, it means that there is a reasonable level of consistency in the pairwise comparisons and that the computed weights are within the acceptable limit. If the reverse is the case ($CR > 0.1$) it means that the weights obtained are inconsistent and need to be checked.

The value of the Consistency index, CI was calculated from the preference matrix according to the equation below

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}$$

λ_{max} is the Principal Eigen Value; n is the number of factors $\lambda_{max} = \Sigma$ of the products between each element of the priority vector and relative weights

$$\lambda_{max} = (3.38 * 0.26) + (4.95 * 0.21) + (6.83 * 0.16) + (10.37 * 0.13) + (16.42 * 0.08) + (18.33 * 0.06) + (24.00 * 0.04) + (26.50 * 0.04) + (36.00 * 0.02)$$

$$\lambda_{max} = 0.87 + 1.05 + 1.07 + 1.31 + 1.32 + 1.08 + 1.04 + 0.94 + 0.88$$

$$\lambda_{max} = 9.56$$

$$CI = (9.56 - 9) / (9 - 1) = 0.07$$

$$CR = 0.07 / 1.46 = 0.047$$

$$CR = 0.047 < 0.10 \text{ (Acceptable)}$$

The Consistency Ratio (CR) is a measure to check how consistent our judgments are in decision-making. If CR is less than 0.10, it means our judgments are reasonably consistent, which is good. We achieved a CR of 0.047, which is below the maximum allowable 0.10. This indicates that the judgments are in good shape and the decision-making process is reliable.

Figure 1: Dam Suitability Map

The suitability map indicates that the village of Umuria has the most suitable areas for dam construction. Upon comparing the suitability map with the elevation map, flow accumulation, and rainfall map, it was observed that all the most suitable areas are situated in the region with lower elevation, higher flow accumulation, and highest precipitation, respectively.

Table 7: Suitability Distribution

S/N	Class_Name	Area (Hectares)	Percentage (%)
1	Most Suitable	8161.65	70
2	Not Suitable	3555.18	30

3.4 Proposed Dam Site

The chosen dam site at Umuria village in Anaku was determined by analyzing an integrated dataset that included factors like the drainage basin, flow accumulation, and pour points. The identified location has a flow accumulation value of 10846. This proposed dam site falls within the 4th stream order, making it particularly suitable. The 4th stream order collects water from orders 1 to 3, underscoring the site's suitability for hosting a dam in Anaku.

Figure 2: Showing the possible site selection process/criteria

Figure 3: Proposed Dam Site

Received: 2 October 2024

Revised: 22 October 2024

Accepted: 25 October 2024

Copyright © authors 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13992484>

4. Conclusion

This study contributes as a case study for identifying suitable dam locations in Anaku, employing the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), a GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis method. Nine criteria, including elevation, slope, drainage network, rainfall, geology, flow accumulation, land use/land cover, soil types, and drainage basin, were considered for dam site selection. Flow accumulation, rainfall, and land cover/land use were the primary criteria. The dam site suitability map revealed that 70% of the study area falls into the "suitable" category, while 30% falls into the "not suitable" category. This indicates that approximately 70% of the study area holds potential for dam site selection. Although a considerable portion appears suitable, only one site, located in Umuria village, was identified as the most suitable and proposed for dam construction due to its classification as a 4th order stream with a flow accumulation region of 10846. This mapping method provides valuable data for decision-makers involved in regional water resources management and sustainable development. It aids in determining optimal sites for constructing new dams, addressing purposes such as irrigation and flood control. The identification of a specific site showcases the economic and natural potential of the study area, emphasizing its importance for dam site selection.

References

1. Baroni, L., Cenci, L., Tettamanti, M., & Berati, M. (2007). Evaluating the environmental impact of various dietary patterns combined with different food production systems. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 61(2), 279–286. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602522>
2. Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). Exploring the Distinctions between Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods. *Think India Journal*, 27(1), 7-15.
3. Hagos, H., Engida, A. N., Hailu, A., & Yohannes, T. (2022). Water scarcity and challenges in developing countries: A systematic review. *Journal of Water Resource and Protection*, 14(4), 135-148. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jwarp.2022.144008>
4. Integrated Regional Basin Management (IRBM). (2010). Water resource management strategy and policy framework. *IRBM Journal*, 6(1), 23-32.
5. Madu, I. A., Eze, B. E., & Chikaire, J. U. (2010). Climate change impacts on agriculture and food security: Implications for sustainable development. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 4(3), 111-118. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJEST09.123>
6. Moe, C. L., & Rheingans, R. D. (2006). Global challenges in water, sanitation and health. *Journal of Water and Health*, 4(S1), 41-57. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wh.2005.039>
7. NBS (National Bureau of Statistics). (2017). *Annual abstract of statistics*. Abuja, Nigeria: National Bureau of Statistics.
8. Nfor, B. N., Agunwamba, J. C., & Mbajiorgu, C. C. (2007). Hydrogeology of the Anambra Basin. *Water Resources Journal*, 18(3), 133-143.
9. Nnadi, F. N., Chikaire, J. U., & Ejiogu-Okereke, N. (2019). Agricultural productivity and rural development: Anambra State, Southeast Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 23(2), 153-164. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jae.v23i2.10>
10. Onugba, J. N., & Yaya, M. B. (2010). Water supply issues and challenges in Anaku, Ayamelum Local Government Area of Anambra State. *International Journal of Water Resources Development*, 26(4), 561-572. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07900627.2010.514313>
11. Patel, R. S., Taneja, S., Singh, J., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). Modelling of Surface Runoff using SWMM and GIS for Efficient Storm Water Management. *CURRENT SCIENCE*, 126(4), 463.

12. Sayl, K. N., & Ali, S. A. (2016). Planning and design criteria for sustainable dams and reservoirs. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 75(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-016-6022-0>
13. Senzanje, A., Boelee, E., & Rusere, S. (2008). Multiple use of water and the impact of small reservoirs on livelihoods in rural Zimbabwe. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, 33(8-13), 762-769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2008.06.045>
14. Shah, Z., Kumar, M. D., & Singh, O. P. (2012). Dams, groundwater, and water shortage in India: A research paper. *Journal of Hydrology*, 6(2), 118-125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2012.03>
15. Sharma, S. N., & Dehalwar, K. (2023). Fundamentals of Planning and Design of Housing.